

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				μ_{eff} B.M.
			M	C	H	N	
1.	[UO ₂ (C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](CH ₃ COO) ₂	Yellowish brown	31.09 (29.10)	47.02 (47.82)	3.31 (3.25)	6.86 (7.00)	0.210
2.	[UO ₂ (C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂	Dark yellow	28.31 (28.10)	46.10 (46.66)	3.05 (2.67)	10.95 (10.45)	0.526
3.	[VO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)]SO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Reddish brown	9.03 (8.70)	47.52 (47.98)	4.20 (4.41)	7.63 (7.01)	1.905
4.	[VO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Brown	8.56 (7.50)	53.62 (53.49)	4.95 (4.23)	11.65 (12.00)	1.655
5.	[TiO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)]C ₂ O ₄ ·4H ₂ O	Brownish black	8.12 (7.90)	56.28 (55.97)	4.96 (4.46)	8.15 (8.80)	0.185
6.	[TiO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Black	7.92 (7.20)	54.62 (53.99)	4.80 (4.25)	12.28 (12.80)	0.299
7.	[ZrO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)]Cl ₂ ·8H ₂ O	Yellowish white	12.95 (12.90)	45.20 (45.88)	4.30 (4.91)	7.16 (7.05)	0.328
8.	[ZrO(C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₄)](SCN) ₂ ·8H ₂ O	Brown	12.22 (11.70)	48.35 (48.82)	5.35 (4.82)	10.28 (10.80)	0.402

orbitals of oxygen atom. The other two bands at 12.50 and 14.70 kK are assigned to be due to electron transition b_2-e^* or ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^2(E) I$ and $b_2 \rightarrow b_1$ or ${}^3B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$. The spectra is thus consistent with a square pyramidal structure for the complex $1^2.1^2$.

The complexes are very stable and remain unchanged on treatment with strong acids or alkalis. No substitution is found to occur when treated with other strong ligands such as di- or tri-amines, while heating with ammonium thiocyanate or oxalate results only in the replacement of anions.

It is thus evident that the ligand is bonded very firmly to oxo metal ion while the bonding of anions is somewhat weaker and hence these undergo replacement. The structure of the complexes can be presented as

where, M = UC^{IV}, VO^{IV}, TiO^{IV}, ZrO^{IV}.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of Junior Research Fellowship.

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Studies on Complexes of Rare Earths with Malonohydroxamic Acid

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Manuscript received 10 July 1980, revised 7 October 1986, accepted 26 November 1986

MALONOHYDROXAMIC acid, HOHN.O.C. CH₂.CO.NHOH, has been used successfully for the determination of a number of metal ions by spectrophotometric, gravimetric as well as chromatographic methods^{1,2}. Rare earth chlorides have been found to react with this ligand yielding compounds of stoichiometry, Ln₂(MHA)_x·xH₂O (where, Ln=Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III}; x=2 or 3; MHA⁻²=malonohydroxamate ion). As an extension to our previous investigations concerning the influence of chelate ring sizes on the coordination number and geometry exhibited by the hydroxamic acid complexes³⁻⁶, we have

prepared and characterised several new rare earth malonohydroxamates.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of reagent grade and their solutions made in double-distilled water. All standard rare earth solutions were prepared by the method described earlier³. Malonohydroxamic acid was prepared by the method as described by Hantzsch⁷. The product was repeatedly recrystallised before use (m.p. 154°). Elemental analyses and infrared spectra confirmed purity of the ligand.

Thermal analyses of the complexes were carried out in a Metrimpex OD-102 derivatograph. The experiments were carried out in air at heating rate 8.0°/min. Elemental analyses were carried out by semimicro method and the metal analyses were carried out as described in the previous communications^{3,4}. Infrared spectra (4 000–600 cm⁻¹) of the complexes in solid state were recorded in nujol with the help of a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

Preparation of complexes: To an aqueous solution of a mixture of rare earth chloride (0.2 M) and ammonium chloride (1 g) was added an aqueous solution of malonohydroxamic acid (0.3 M) in slight excess with stirring, followed by a dropwise addition of ammonia solution (1:10) to adjust pH to 4–6. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for about 20 min with occasional stirring until the precipitate separated completely from the clear solution in a granular form. The compounds were collected by filtration, washed several times with hot water and finally with ethanol (95%, v/v) and then dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) indicate that the stoichiometry of the complexes is Ln₂(MHA)_x·xH₂O (where Ln=Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III}; x=2 or 3). Table 1 also shows the results obtained from the DTA curves. The endothermic peaks of the DTA curves of the hydrated Sm^{III}

and Gd^{III} malonohydroxamate complexes indicated the loss of water with the decomposition of the ligand.

The infrared spectra show close similarity to the spectra of oximes and oxalohydroxamic acid⁸. The peculiarities shown by the ligand is possibly arising out of the placement of two hydroxamic acid groups in the ligand, not on adjacent carbon atoms as in oxalohydroxamic acid, but separated by a —CH₂— bridge. In the free ligand, the band at 1 700 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to C=O stretching vibration, whereas in the sodium salt of the ligand, this band shifted to 1 600 cm⁻¹. In the case of rare earth complexes, the same band shifted to longer wavelengths (1 590 for Pr^{III}, 1 585 for Nd^{III}, 1 590 for Sm^{III}, and 1 595 cm⁻¹ for Gd^{III} malonohydroxamates), and these shiftings surely depict the coordination of the type —C=O · Ln—O. For the free ligand, there occurs three sharp but well defined bands at 900–1 100 cm⁻¹ (e.g. 940s, 995s and 1 070s). The NO stretching vibrations have generally been found at 900–1 000 cm⁻¹ in different hydroxamic acids. As in oxalohydroxamic acid⁸, NO band is found to occur at 1 020 cm⁻¹, it is rather difficult to assign any one of the above bands as the actual NO stretching bands. In the case of sodium malonohydroxamate, three bands are found at 935s, 985s and 1 060s cm⁻¹, whereas in the hydrated rare earth-malonohydroxamates these bands are found respectively at 932w, 995s, 1 074s in Pr^{III}, 933vw, 992s, 1 080s, in Nd^{III}, 932w, 995w, 995s, 1 078s in Sm^{III}, and 930w, 998s, 1 080s cm⁻¹ in Gd^{III}-malonohydroxamates. From the above data, it transpires that the 940s cm⁻¹ band of the free ligand is the actual stretching band for NO, because in the case of simple salt as well as the rare earth complexes, the free ligand band is found to shift to longer wavelengths with reduction of intensity as observed for the hydrated rare earth oxalohydroxamates.

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd *	Analysis % :		% Loss at	
	Found/(Calcd.)		115–120°	Decomp.
			Found/ (Calcd.)	Temp. °C
Pr ₂ (MHA) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	34.41 (38.52)	11.30 (11.48)	7.36 (7.37)	55–115
Nd ₂ (MHA) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	39.00 (39.06)	11.25 (11.37)	7.00 (7.31)	50–120
Sm ₂ (MHA) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	40.00 (40.04)	11.00 (11.18)	—	—
Gd ₂ (MHA) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	41.30 (41.35)	11.20 (11.40)	—	—

*MHA²⁻ = C₂H₄N₂O₄²⁻.